

CONSULTING CHILDREN: MATHS AND ME

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This paper examines what teaching and learning mathematics 'looked like' and how it was experienced by children across eight Irish primary classrooms at second (7 and 8 years old) and fifth (10 and 11 years old) class level. Children are at the heart of the learning process and can provide important views of the curriculum and of the teaching and learning. Exploring children's experiences of teaching and learning provide insights into the difficulties and challenges children experience in their learning. A total of twenty four mathematics lessons were observed, while eighteen mathematics lessons were video recorded. Focus group interview with children, child questionnaires and drawings were also employed in the data collection. For the majority of children in this study mathematics is little more than calculation and number work. Despite the Primary Mathematics curriculum advocating mathematical processes such as problem solving, developing logic and reasoning, and communicating mathematical ideas, in this study few children talked about mathematics in this way. Children's beliefs about mathematics are determined by the mathematics they encounter, the tasks in which they encounter it and their disposition towards mathematics as a result of previous encounters.

INTRODUCTION

Pupil voice has come to be seen as crucially important to understanding the complexities of learning in school. Children's understandings of classroom processes, and their own role in learning, have gained attention in research studies both nationally and internationally (Alexander, 2010; Barber & Houssart, 2013; Devine, 2011; Gipps & Tunstall, 1998). This research seeks to give 'voice' to children's views and perspectives on mathematics learning. In order to best understand how perspectives are formed, it is necessary to go inside classrooms and situate teaching and learning in social context and to examine the variables (hidden and overt) that exert an influence.

According to social practice theory, students come to the classroom as part of many diverse communities in which they have formed their identities and they have to reshape their identities as they participate in the community of the classroom. It is in this reshaping of identity that learning resides (Lee, 2006). "Identities are constructed within a context of activity, pupils build an identity, that is a way that they explain themselves, within each community in which they participate" (Holland, Skinner, Lachicotte, & Cain, 1998 p. 270). Similarly, "Mathematics in practice becomes an issue of identity as well as cognitive process" (Barta & Bremner, 2009 p.91). Enabling students to build an identity as someone who is able to do mathematics is an important aim for a mathematics classroom. Teachers are the most important resource for developing student's mathematical identities (Cobb & Hodge, 2002; Hayes, Mills, Christie, & Lingard, 2006). They influence the ways in which student's think of themselves as learners (Walshaw, 2004). While learning mathematical skills and knowledge, students are also developing beliefs and attitudes about the subject, and themselves as mathematical learners and practitioners (Grootenboer, 2013). Teachers of mathematics are in

a powerful position because they can significantly impact on the mathematical identity and the futures of learners through the nature of the relational pedagogy they practice in their classrooms. This is evident throughout the everyday, routine mathematics classes that teachers and students experience. Feedback is a crucial feature of the teaching-learning process. Bloom (1976) identifies feedback, correctives and reinforcements (such as praise, blame, encouragement and other rewards and punishments that are used to sustain learning) as important elements of the instructional process. Feedback is considered to be one of the structuring conditions for learning, and is included alongside such variables as task presentation, sequencing, level and pacing of content and teacher expectations (Gipps & Tunstall, 1998). A major determinant of self-esteem is feedback from others, therefore children's self-evaluations are very often a reflection of significant others' evaluations, such as parents, teachers and peers. As far as academic self-esteem is concerned, teachers' evaluations are the most important, particularly in the early years of schooling. Children develop their 'self-image' in school through observing and feeling not only how the teacher interacts with them, but also how the teacher interacts with the rest of the class (Crocker & Cheeseman, 1988). The development of a positive self-concept in children is dependent upon perceiving themselves as successful, this in turn may depend on the way the child interprets the teachers' reaction to his/her performances.

According to Walls (2009) the right/wrong nature of mathematics as presented by teachers, textbooks, families and peers through social interactions, significantly contribute to student's mathematical identities and construct of themselves as a learner of mathematics. Rowland (1995) argues that a child's level of mathematical competence cannot and should not be judged by the child's offering of a 'correct answer'. Rowland suggests that when a child volunteers an answer that is not the 'expected' teacher answer, it is important to investigate and explicate the child's thinking and reasoning behind it. With reference to the linguist Lakoff, Rowland (1995) demonstrates how in oral explanations, students use "hedgies" (such as about, maybe, probably, around) as "a 'shield' against being wrong" (p. 350). The rewards and privileges that come with being correct are great. Rowland (1995) observes that there is a regrettable absence of regard for the role 'uncertainty' plays in the mathematics classroom. Teachers, and in turn students, fail to recognise that being in a state of 'uncertainty' is a necessary precondition to learning and that in "the making and learning of mathematics, uncertainty is to be expected, acknowledged and explicit" (Rowland, 1995 p.328). Recent research carried out by Boaler (2013) into ability and mindset in the mathematics classroom reveals that the types of tasks chosen by teachers communicate powerful messages regarding what mathematics and knowledge is important. Tasks convey what doing mathematics is all about. By engaging in tasks, students develop ideas about the nature of mathematics and mathematics learning (Anthony & Walshaw, 2009; Hodge, Zhao, Visnovska, & Cobb, 2007). If children are assigned short, closed mathematics questions that have right or wrong answers and children are regularly getting them incorrect, it is very difficult to sustain the opinion that high achievement is possible with effort. In contrast, when tasks are open, with opportunities for learning, children can see the possibility of greater achievement and respond to these opportunities to improve (Boaler, 2013).

METHODOLOGY

The study employs a mixed methods design approach (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009) across eight primary school classrooms at second and fifth class level. A total of twenty four mathematics lessons were observed, while eighteen mathematics lessons were video recorded. Focus group interviews with children, child questionnaires and drawings were also employed in the data collection.

FINDINGS

Observations of mathematics lessons at second class level showed teaching of both the Measurement and Shape and Space strands of the curriculum. However, the children themselves when interviewed did not make reference to this as mathematics until prompted about the lesson and only then it was about “clocks”. Another group of children categorised their mathematics learning into what they termed to be “real maths” and what was not, with importance attached to copy work.

Kim: Real maths is doing sums in our copies

Researcher: And doing 2D shapes like you were today, is that real maths?

Joey: No, no...

Researcher: Well what would you call that?

Kim: I would just call it shapes.

This narrow view of mathematics was supported when children in all the research schools were invited to draw a picture of what ‘doing maths’ looks like. Many of the drawings consisted of a “table, a chair and me writing down a sum.” accompanied with “my maths sheet”. The physicality of doing mathematics is described both in the children’s own words and in their drawings:

I am sitting on a chair and my bag is on the back of me chair and I’m doing my maths.

For older children mathematics involved carrying out exercises in computation work, “taking sums off the board”, “writing them into my copy”, “with my head down and like doing like rough work to try to sort it out.” As children got older ‘doing maths’ became quickly established as a form of individual written task referred to as ‘work’. In follow up interviews some teachers appeared to disassociate their teaching practices with children’s views of mathematics:

A lot of kids just find maths you know it’s something that you’re doing out of a copy or you are just looking at the board.

Unless they have a whole page of numbers to add or take away or something they don’t see it as maths, even last week we were doing chance with dice and they said ‘we didn’t do maths today’, I said ‘yeah we did’...if it’s not written down in adding and things they don’t see it as maths. Even when we were doing lines and angles because they weren’t specifically doing stuff in a copy, they weren’t doing maths, they didn’t do maths. Yeah they don’t associate it being fun at all so they just think maths is boring and you just have to accept it that’s they’re understanding of it.

Teacher accounts reveal a lack of awareness of the messages communicated to children within their community of practice. Messages about what constitutes as important mathematics are daily reinforced across classrooms both overtly and covertly through teacher actions and words. One group of second class children welcomed the freedom of using mental strategies over pencil and paper:

Cody: It is much more fun when you are doing them in your head.

Researcher: Why is it more fun when you do it in your head?

Kim: Because it's a hassle to write it all down.

Cody: Because writing takes up your page.

Children's descriptions and drawings were strongly supported by classroom observations of the salient role writing plays in the mathematics classroom as exemplified by Figure 1 below.

<p>Figure 1: Writing in Mathematics Copy</p>	<p>Figure 2: A Child's Demonstration of Repeated Subtraction</p>

Confusion in the Mathematics Classroom

In this study fifth class children admitted to difficulties in understanding and expressed strong feelings of confusion in their accounts and drawings “I would draw meself confused doing the sums because it does be too hard”. For the children in one fifth class feeling confused was a common experience shared by the group:

Teachers ask more questions than they say answers.

He doesn't really help us...he just tells us what to ...like ok 'carry this on, add this number here...and we're just thinking...What?!

Sometimes you don't get something and then you don't get what they are trying to explain and you don't get the other way they are trying to explain at all...

You can pay attention and just not 'get' what is going on.

Feelings of being confused were not confined to fifth class alone as children in one 2nd Class shared their experience:

This is what happens, sometimes she mixes up the questions and there was a minus sum and then she goes onto an adding sum and then she goes back to the minus sum and then she wants the answer...

The procedures and processes involved in computation caused great difficulty for many children. Some children made reference to tricks used by teachers to help in the explanation and understanding of challenging concepts such as long multiplication and the ‘magic zero’ “I get mixed up on long multiplication because when there are two digits, I keep just doing it like one digit and I always keep forgetting me magic zero” ;“And then the other night....it was divide 742 divided by 42 and you had to take it away and like you had to take away 17 times, say 742 take away 42.” (Keith). Supplied with some paper and a pencil, Keith proceeded to write down the sum as shown in Figure 2 above.

The practice of executing mathematical procedures without understanding was an experience communicated by many children. According to one fifth class child not enough time was allocated by teachers to the teaching and explaining of mathematical content that children were required to know:

we did an assessment test and there was one thing, use your long division and I skipped it completely because I didn’t know what to do...I had just forgotten how to do long division.

I hate it. I think when they are teaching it, they do it for a week and then they just leave it, but I think...because now I forget long division....they should do it all the time.

The emphasis on procedure left many children grappling to understand the mathematical concepts underlying these procedures:

the yoke where....you had to divide by the bottom, multiply by the top. ..and some of them are a bit annoying because you have to switch them back...

decimal points....I can’t get my head around sometimes...I understand how many places you have to go back but then when it gets into bigger numbers...I just get confused.

Time...I don’t get time...I just can’t get my head around it... it’s kind of confusing...because usually when you are carrying over...lets say, 10 minus 11, you would have to carry over something, but when it is with time, you have to bring over like a 6 and everything and leave behind this....it is confusing.”

Children were left feeling disempowered and disconnected from the important mathematical processes necessary in order to succeed. Images of being ‘confused’ when doing mathematics appeared on a number of drawings by fifth class children.

<p>Figure 3: Drawings of Confusion in the Mathematics Classroom</p>	<p>Figure 4: Being Confused</p>

Other children mentioned processes such as ‘thinking’ when asked what their drawings would look like “I probably do one with my book and the table and have my pencil banging against

my head thinking”. “this is what I’d draw, I would have myself like that and I would be just stuck there in time, I would be like ‘what the hell, what is this?’

Emotions and Attitudes towards Mathematics

Children expressed different thoughts and feelings about mathematics. Children’s attitudes towards mathematics were communicated through their interviews and their drawings.

- Researcher: If I was to mention the word maths to you, what would your image of maths be?
- Chelsy: School...awful...I hate it...
- Declan: Writing.
- Diana: Maths to me would be I don’t like it...
- Samantha: Writing or like a book.
- Researcher: A book like your maths book?
- Samantha: Yeah Mathemagic
- Researcher: What about you, what would come to mind?
- Eddie: It’s boring.
- Chelsy: I don’t really like maths but if someone said to me I would probably think ‘my future’. It is kind of everything. I don’t want to end up like a hobo on the street because I didn’t learn my maths.
- Frank: I like doing the hard sums
- Researcher: And what are hard sums?
- Frank: Hard sums are in the hundreds and the two hundreds and the five hundreds.
- Tom: “I like the challenge of trying to get the answer, say it could be one you never learned before.”.

Positive dispositions towards mathematics were represented in children’s drawings with ‘love hearts’ and smiling, happy faces. Negative dispositions towards the subject were accompanied with words in the form of thought bubbles expressing feelings of confusion or boredom.

In a questionnaire of 164 respondents, 91% of children believed that mathematics was different to other subjects. For the children in this study mathematics was different by virtue of being ‘easier’ or ‘harder’. For some fifth class children ‘it’s easy than most subjects’ and for others ‘you have to pay attention all the time and it’s. The questionnaire found 51% of second class children always liked the work they did in mathematics class with 55% of children feeling they could do a good job on their mathematics tasks. For fifth class children only 20% admitted to always liking what they did in mathematics with 44% of children feeling they could do a good job on their mathematics tasks. Children expressed their desire for ‘less writing’, preference to ‘work in pairs and in groups’, together with the call for mathematics to be more hands on ‘if we got to do experiments with water to show how litres work’. Among second class children opinion varied from ‘maths is cool’, ‘I don’t like it as much as Art, P.E, yard and Science’ to ‘I learn the most from maths’. 48% of second class

children and 70% of fifth class children believed that to be great at mathematics one must work very hard.

The Relevance of Mathematics

“It’s the most important subject but they make it so boring.” Children across all of the eight research schools recognised the importance and relevance of mathematics to their lives both now and in the future. According to one group of fifth class children mathematics was ‘boring’ but “if they could make it interesting, kind of put it in more a story way like, this is millimetre dude or something like that” their experience of this subject would be better. However, despite some children’s rather negative experience of mathematics, its importance as a subject was recognised. Mathematics was considered important when it came to the practical, day to day aspects of life such as shopping “if you go to a shop and you don’t know maths the shopkeeper could make you pay extra” and television “if you want to watch the telly, you won’t know what number the kid’s station is on if you don’t do maths.”. For others mathematics is something that is useful when you are older and “doing something important...say you are a bank accountant or something. Mathematics was recognised by other children as playing a key role in determining their life chances as they get older “it will help you have a better future” and “so I can get in to a good college”.

CONCLUSION

For the majority of children in this study mathematics is little more than calculation and number work. Despite the Revised Primary Mathematics Curriculum 1999 advocating mathematical processes such as problem solving, developing logic and reasoning, and communicating mathematical ideas, in this study few children talked about mathematics in this way. Only two children in fifth class referred to general cognitive processes such as learning and thinking. Children’s beliefs about mathematics are determined by the mathematics they encounter, the tasks in which they encounter it and their disposition towards mathematics as a result of previous encounters. A distinctive feature of their drawings revealed that individual written work was repeatedly experienced by the children during mathematics, and what they most identified as “doing maths”. Observations of mathematics lessons, teachers’ and children’s descriptions of a typical lesson, and examination of children’s mathematics copies for evidence of frequency of written tasks, supported these claims.

REFERENCES

- Alexander, R. (Ed.). (2010). *Children, their world, their education: Final report and recommendations of the Cambridge primary review*. London and New York: Routledge Taylor and Francis Group.
- Barber, P., & Houssart, J. (2013). Eliciting pupil perspectives in primary mathematics: Possibilities and issues. *International Journal of Primary, Elementary and Early Years Education*, 1-15.

- Barta, J., & Bremner, M. (2009). Seeing with many eyes: Connections between anthropology and mathematics. In B. Greer, S. Mukhopadhyay, A. Powell & S. Nelson-Barber (Eds.), *Culturally responsive mathematics education* (pp. 85-109). New York: Routledge.
- Boaler, J. (2013). Ability and mathematics: the mindset revolution that is reshaping education. *FORUM*, 55(1), 143-152.
- Cobb, P., & Hodge, L. L. (2002). A relational perspective on issues of cultural diversity and equity as they play out in the mathematics classroom. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 4, 249-284.
- Crocker, A.C., & Cheeseman, R.G. (1988). The ability of young children to rank themselves for academic ability. *Educational Studies*, 14(1), 105-110.
- Devine, D. (2011). *Immigration and schooling in the Republic of Ireland: Making a difference?* Manchester and New York: Manchester University Press.
- Gipps, C., & Tunstall, P. (1998). Effort, ability and the teacher: Young children's explanations for success and failure. *Oxford Review of Education*, 24(2), 149-165.
- Grootenboer, P. (2013). The praxis of mathematics teaching: developing mathematical identities. *Pedagogy, Culture and Society*, 21(2), 321-342.
- Hayes, D., Mills, M., Christie, P., & Lingard, B. (2006). *Teachers and schooling making a difference. Productive pedagogies, assessment and performance*. NSW: Allen & Unwin.
- Hodge, L., Zhao, Q., Visnovska, J., & Cobb, P. (2007). What does it mean for an instructional task to be effective? In J. Watson & K. Beswick (Eds.), *Mathematics: Essential research, essential practice (Vol. 1, pp. 329-401)*. Hobart: MERGA.
- Holland, D., Skinner, D., Lachicotte, W., & Cain, C. (1998). *Identity and agency in cultural worlds*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Lee, C. (2006). *Language for learning mathematics: Assesment for learning in practice*. Open University Press.
- Rowland, T. (1995). Between the lines: The language of mathematics. In J. Anghileri (Ed.), *Children's mathematical thinking in the primary years: Perspectives on children's learning*. London: Continuum.
- Walshaw, M. (2004). A powerful theory of active engagement. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 24(3), 4-10.
- Walls, F. (2009). *Mathematical subjects: Children talk about their mathematics lives*: Springer.